

Is Multiple Sclerosis Preventable?

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Introduction

Multiple Sclerosis is an autoimmune disease, which means the inflammatory mediators in a patient's body are attacking the myelin sheaths of several central or peripheral nerves. Myelin sheaths are coverings for nerves that maintain the electric impulse that goes through the axon of neurons isolated from the environment at large. When these are destroyed by inflammatory mediators in variable degrees, symptoms and disability shows.

The most common age to exhibit the symptoms are between 20-25 years of age and most commonly presented in white females. One of the hallmark signs of the disease is having different and diverse symptomatic episodes that would present months to years apart and affect different body regions.

Common Signs and Symptoms include:

- Sensory Loss, which is an early complain.
- Motor Anomalies at the level of the spine, Spasticity and cramping.
- Autonomic disorders at the spine level, Bladder, Bowel or Sexual dysfunction
- Cerebellar symptoms: Dysarthria (Problems with speech), Nystagmus (Eye deviation), Tremors (Shaking)
- Neuralgia: Nervous pain, most commonly Trigeminal (Facial motor/sensory nerve upper division)
- Psychiatric: Depression, Euphoria

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Classification

This disease can be classified in a clinical criteria basis:

- Relapsing Remitting Multiple Sclerosis, the most common. It presents itself, cures and then presents again.
- Secondary Progressive
- Primary Progressive
- Progressive Relapsing

Rare cases are:

- Isolated syndrome: a unique and only episode.
- Benign, the one that complete remits.

Diagnostics

There is no FDA approved diagnostic method currently available, which leaves MS as a rule out diagnosis.

This disease is diagnosed through clinical and laboratory tests.

Clinically, tested for the above-mentioned symptoms.

In the Lab and Imaging studies,

- Magnetic Resonance Imaging, which will show white lesions (scarring where the lesions happened)
- Lumbar puncture, invasive procedure to obtain cerebrospinal fluid that will show oligoclonal bands and increased immunoglobulin G production.
- Evoked potentials, electrical currents that evoke a muscle function.
- Serological Specific Biomarkers – under development

Fig 2. Epstein-Barr virus as a cause of multiple sclerosis: opportunities for prevention and therapy. (Reused with Permission)

Treatment

There are no curative treatments available for MS.

Nanoparticles could potentially be the solution to deliver the drug at site avoiding the physiological barriers that the BBB and BCSFB pose due to their small size.

By using nanoparticles, we can improve how well medications dissolve, target them to specific areas, reduce side effects from high doses, and control how quickly the drugs are released.

The prospective treatment and management depends on 2 aspects:

- Immunomodulation to decrease the autoimmune disorder
- Symptomatic modifiers (to decrease symptoms)

Immunomodulators medications for this disease:

Steroids, Prednisolone for acute (short time of onset) symptoms

Plasma Exchange for Severe short term attacks

Dexamethasone other kind of steroids for complications, such as transverse myelitis

Symptomatic medications for this disease:

Pain: Antidepressants, tricyclic.

Spasticity, (cramping): Baclofen.

Depression: Antidepressants, SSRIs.

Fatigue: Fluoxetine, Amantadine

Discussion

Multiple Sclerosis has been linked to the Epstein Barr Virus (Herpesviridae, subfamily Gamaherpesvirinae, genus Lymphocryptovirus, species Human herpesvirus 4) the same that causes mononucleosis; (habitat and reservoir are human blood cells and throat white cells (lymphocytes) opening the possibility of having antivirals and vaccinations to prevent contracting or suffering for it. There has been no linkage to other viruses yet, however research on the topic is still ongoing.

Blood Brain Barrier Video Used under CC © belongs to original authors

Fig. 3: Potential mechanisms of antibody pathogenicity in multiple sclerosis (Reused with Permission)

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